
Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel's Contributions to National Security and Nationalism

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ABSTRACT

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, known as the "Iron Man of India", played a key role in the country's post-independence history through his dedication to national unity, strategic foresight, and diplomatic skill. His most notable achievement was the integration of over 560 princely states into the Indian Union, which he accomplished through a mix of persuasion, diplomacy, and decisive action, particularly in areas such as Hyderabad, Junagadh, and Kashmir. Beyond his political triumphs, Patel contributed significantly to national security by establishing the All-India Services, which have been crucial to India's administrative stability and progress. Patel's approach to national security is consistent with the principles articulated by Harold Lasswell and Harold Brown, who emphasize sovereignty, territorial integrity, and economic stability. Patel's initiatives to unify India by merging princely states and establishing strong administrative and police services, the IAS and IPS, were crucial for ensuring peace and stability in the newly independent nation. Patel also recognised the strategic importance of military preparedness and border security, especially in relation to the continuing threats posed by Pakistan and the expansionist ambitions of China, especially after its occupation of Tibet. Patel's farsightedness and cautious approach to China's intentions were a sharp contrast to Prime Minister Nehru's idealistic approach. While Nehru favoured

appeasement and international cooperation, Patel advocated a more strategic and cautious foreign policy, emphasising military preparedness and national security. His warnings about China's territorial ambitions and the need for a robust defence stance were prophetic, highlighting the enduring geopolitical challenges facing India. In the area of nationalism, Patel's pragmatic approach and focus on unity were evident in his efforts to integrate the princely states and promote a coherent national identity. His emphasis on secularism, protection of minority rights and promotion of Hindi as the national language underscored his inclusive vision. Patel's legacy, marked by his commitment to national unity, administrative efficiency and strategic foresight, continues to inspire and guide India's path towards a strong, united and prosperous future.

Introduction

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, popularly known as the "Iron Man of India", played a key role in shaping modern India. His contributions to Indian national security and nationalism played a vital role in transforming the country from a fragmented colony to a unified and sovereign nation. Sardar Patel believed that the nation should be built on the basis of reason, democracy, secularism, civil liberties, equality and social justice. He opposed the use of culture, religion and community identity for nation building. He also believed that sovereignty should lie with the people, not the king. Patel had initiated Aatmanirbhar Bharat. He believed that India should be economically self-sufficient in essentials such as food production. He supported the management of the corporate life of the village by a popularly elected panchayat. Patel believed that political independence should be combined with economic independence. Patel stressed the need to promote Indian self-reliance and self-confidence. Patel prioritized secular citizenship over fundamentalism such as caste, religion and ethnicity. He opposed separate electorates and communal representation. This article traces Patel's life, his strategic insights into national security, and his unwavering commitment to fostering the spirit of nationalism.

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel's Life Sketch

Vallabhbhai Jhaverbhai Patel was born into a farming family in Nadiad, Kheda district, Gujarat, on October 31, 1875. Vallabhbhai's father Jhaverbhai was a small farmer in Karamsad village. Known for his honesty and simplicity, the villagers often sought his advice and help in times of crisis. It is reported that Jhaverbhai was involved in the significant 1857 Rebellion led by the Jhansi ki Rani. Vallabhbhai, it appears, inherited his father's aptitude for organizing and strategizing campaigns and movements.

He attended primary school in Karamasad and high school in Petlad, but was mainly self-educated. Patel married at the age of 16, passed matriculation at the age of 22, and passed the district advocate's examination, which gave him the opportunity to practice law. In 1900 he established an independent office of the district advocate in Godhra and two years later he moved to Borsad.

In August 1910 Patel went to London to study at the Middle Temple. There he studied diligently and passed the final examination with high honours. Returning to India in February 1913 he settled in Ahmedabad, and became a leading barrister in criminal law at the Ahmedabad Bar. Restrained and modest, he was known for his excellent manners, his smart, English-style clothes, and his championships at bridge at the fashionable Gujarat Club in Ahmedabad. Until 1917 he was indifferent to Indian political activities.

Patel found the direction of his life changed after he became influenced by Mohandas K. Gandhi in 1917. Patel followed Gandhi's satyagraha (policy of nonviolence) in so far as it furthered the Indian struggle against the British.

From 1917 to 1924, Patel served as the inaugural Indian municipal commissioner of Ahmedabad. Subsequently, he was elected municipal president from 1924 to 1928. Patel first made his mark in 1918, when he organised a massive campaign of peasants, agriculturalists and landowners of Kaira in Gujarat against the Bombay government's decision to collect the full annual revenue tax despite crop failures due to heavy rains.

After the Kheda campaign (1918), Gandhiji, while honouring Vallabhbhai, said:: “The skill of a leader is judged by the ability of his assistants to carry out his plans. Many people were ready to follow my advice, but I could not decide who should be my deputy commander. Then I thought of Vallabhbhai. I must confess that when I first met Vallabhbhai, I could not help wondering who this stern-looking man was and whether he would be able to do what I wanted. But the more I got to know him, the more I realised

that I must take his help.” (*Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel Vol-1, Narhari Parikh, Navjivan Prakashan, Ahmedabad. Page 89*)

In 1928 Patel successfully led the resistance of the Bardoli zamindars against rising taxes. His skillful leadership of the Bardoli campaign earned him the title Sardar "leader", and he was thereafter acknowledged as a nationalist leader throughout India. He was regarded as pragmatic, decisive, and even ruthless, and the British recognised him as a dangerous enemy.

Patel's most notable achievement came after India gained independence in 1947, when he became the first Deputy Prime Minister and Minister of Home Affairs. Patel's steadfast dedication to national integration in the newly independent nation led to him being honored with the title "Iron Man of India." He is recognized as the "patron saint of India's civil servants" for his significant role in the founding of the contemporary All India civil services system.. The world's tallest statue, the Statue of Unity, built by the Government of India at a cost of US\$420 million, was dedicated to him on 31 October 2018 and stands at a height of approximately 182 metres (597 ft).

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel’s Contribution to National Security

"The distinctive meaning of national security means freedom from foreign dictation."

(Harold Lasswell, 1950)

Harold Lasswell's assertion that national security is about freedom from foreign dictate underscores the supreme importance of sovereignty and independence. This principle, fundamental to a nation's ability to exercise self-determination, safeguard its interests, and pursue its foreign policy objectives, was championed by men like Sardar Patel in India's struggle for freedom from British colonial rule. Patel's tireless efforts to strengthen India's sovereignty and territorial integrity exemplify the practical application of Lasswell's theoretical framework.

Sardar Patel's contribution to national security is most prominently reflected in his efforts to integrate the princely states into the Indian Union. At the time of independence, India was a conglomeration of British-administered provinces and over 500 princely states, each of which had the option of joining India, Pakistan or remaining independent. Patel's diplomatic acumen and strategic foresight were crucial in persuading most of these states to join India. His approach involved negotiation, political pressure and,

when necessary, the use of force, as seen in the integration of Hyderabad and Junagadh. Patel's successful integration of these states laid the foundation for a unified and secure India.

Patel also focused on strengthening the internal security apparatus. He played a key role in the establishment and organisation of the Indian Administrative Service (IAS) and the Indian Police Service (IPS), ensuring a strong administrative structure for maintaining law and order in the newly independent nation. His emphasis on a disciplined and efficient bureaucracy was crucial in addressing the challenges of a diverse and newly formed country.

"National security then is the ability to preserve the nation's physical integrity and territory; to maintain its economic relations with the rest of the world on reasonable terms; to preserve its nature, institution, and governance from disruption from outside; and to control its borders." (Harold Brown, U.S. Secretary of Defense, 1977-1981)

Harold Brown's definition of national security aligns seamlessly with Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel's contributions to India's security, encompassing multiple dimensions.

- **Physical Integrity and Territorial Security**

Harold Brown has emphasized on the security of the physical boundaries and territory of the nation. Sardar Patel played an important role in integrating various princely states into the Indian Union. This integration of territory was an important step in securing the physical integrity of India and establishing clear boundaries.

- **Economic Security**

Brown highlighted the importance of economic stability and international economic relations. Patel recognised the importance of a strong economy for the nation's security. Sardar Patel envisioned a rapidly industrialised India to reduce external dependency and modernise the armed forces. However, he recognised the importance of agricultural revival to address unemployment and poverty. He advocated a balanced economic approach, emphasising investment-led growth, savings and increased production. Patel rejected short-term solutions and favoured a long-term strategy based on sound economic principles and pragmatic policies.

- **Political and Social Security**

Brown stressed the need to safeguard the nation's political system and social fabric. Patel played a key role in shaping India's democratic institutions and promoting national unity. He worked tirelessly to suppress communal tensions and ensure a smooth transfer of power from British colonial rule to Indian self-government.

- **Border Security**

Brown emphasizes the importance of border control. Patel's efforts in securing India's borders, particularly in the disputed areas of Kashmir and Hyderabad, were crucial in maintaining the country's territorial integrity. He also played a key role in establishing a strong Border Security Force to protect India's borders.

Sardar Patel's Views on India's National Security and Geopolitical Challenges: Insights on Kashmir, Pakistan, Tibet and China

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel's strategic vision anticipated India's future security threats. He advocated decisive military action in Kashmir during the 1947 tribal invasion, recognising Pakistan's enduring hostility. In addition, he also saw the dangers of China's expansionist ambitions, especially after its occupation of Tibet. Patel emphasised the imperative of military preparedness and a cautious foreign policy to safeguard India's sovereignty and regional stability.

- **Sardar Patel's stance on Kashmir and Pakistan**

The differences between Nehru and Patel grew further in the case of Pakistan. In this case Gandhi himself was the main player against Patel. He went on an indefinite fast in protest against Patel's stopping the payment of Rs 55 crore to Pakistan. (Basu, 2014).

Patel had wisely deferred the payment until the issue of Kashmir and the plight of the Hindu minority there was resolved to the satisfaction of all stakeholders. India was under no obligation to pay the entire amount at once. However, Gandhi's silence and his declining health forced Patel to give in to his demands. While Patel respected Nehru's wishes regarding Kashmir, their disagreements on the issue have often been overlooked (Basu, 2014).

Nehru's approach, which allowed Kashmir to retain an Islamic identity, has been praised by his supporters. However, critics argue that Nehru's actions, along with tarnishing the reputation of the Hindu Maharaja Hari Singh, have contributed to the ongoing Kashmir conflict (Basu, 2014). However, this statement is incorrect. Nehru's precondition for accession was that the Maharaja hand over power to Sheikh Abdullah, who did not represent either the Hindu or Sikh populations and whose popularity among Muslims, even in the highly polarised atmosphere he had helped create, was questionable (Singh, 2011, p. 242).

Nehru viewed Sheikh Abdullah as crucial to both dismantling the two-nation theory and establishing India's secular credentials (Singh, 2011, p. 242). However, his decision to internationalize the Kashmir issue at the UN, primarily for personal gain, and his unwarranted promise of a plebiscite, further complicated the situation. It was Patel who ultimately saved the day, as evidenced by General Sam Manekshaw's account of Patel's decisive intervention in ordering the airlift of Indian troops to prevent the fall of Srinagar during the 1948 Indo-Pak war (Jha, 1996). Patel later admitted to Baxi Ghulam Mohammad his inability to resolve the Kashmir issue due to a lack of Nehru's trust (Chopra, 2002, p. 274).

- **Sardar Patel's stance on Tibet and China**

Sardar Patel and Jawaharlal Nehru had different views about China and Tibet. While Nehru, driven by his vision of Asian unity, favoured appeasement of China, Patel was more cautious. Nehru's recognition of Chinese sovereignty over Tibet in 1954, despite the unresolved border issue, was a strategic blunder. Patel, on the other hand, had already foreseen the potential threat posed by China's control over Tibet. He advocated a proactive approach without resorting to imperialism, a distinct characteristic of Indian civilisation. Patel warned Nehru about China's expansionist ambitions, but his concerns were dismissed. Nehru's faith in China's peaceful intentions, rooted in shared experiences of colonial oppression, blinded him to the reality of China's growing assertiveness. Patel and Nehru's divergent views on Sino-Indian relations highlight the far-reaching consequences of contrasting approaches to foreign policy and strategic miscalculations.

On November 7, 1950, Sardar Patel wrote a letter to Prime Minister Nehru, highlighting the grave implications of China's military incursion into Tibet earlier that year. Patel warned that this development forced India to adopt a two-front defence strategy, a necessity unprecedented in centuries. He underlined

Tibet's strategic importance, emphasising the radical change in India's security landscape. Patel urged a comprehensive reassessment of India's defence posture in light of China's territorial expansion. His visionary comments continue to resonate today, serving as a stark reminder of the enduring geopolitical challenges facing India.

While Western imperialism and Chinese irredentism and communist imperialism differ in their methods, the latter is arguably more insidious due to its ideological cloak. This disguise masks underlying racial, national, and historical claims, making it a potent and dangerous force.

India's security landscape has evolved, with traditional threats from the west and northwest persisting while a new challenge emerges from the north and northeast. This dual-front scenario, unprecedented in centuries, necessitates a fundamental shift in India's defense strategy.

Sardar Patel's prescient warning about the threat posed by China's control of Tibet aligns with the Tibetan government's plea to the United Nations on November 7, 1950. The Tibetan appeal, while acknowledging the futility of resisting Chinese aggression, underscores the international community's responsibility to halt such actions.

India's 1954 Sino-Indian Agreement on Trade with Tibet, which enshrined the principles of Peaceful Coexistence or Panchsheel, inadvertently legitimized China's military occupation of Tibet. Dr. Bhimrao Ambedkar, a prominent Indian statesman, expressed deep skepticism about the sincerity of China's commitment to these principles.

He pointed out the stark contradiction between China's professed adherence to Panchsheel and its harsh treatment of Buddhists within its own borders. Ambedkar warned the Indian Prime Minister that China's growing influence in Tibet posed a significant threat to India's security. He cautioned that by allowing China to consolidate its control over Tibet, India had inadvertently facilitated the deployment of Chinese forces along its borders, potentially endangering India's territorial integrity.

Patel's astute assessment of the Chinese threat was shared by others. He was prepared to challenge Nehru's foreign policy during a crucial cabinet meeting scheduled for 21 November 1950. With the support of Rajagopalachari and KM Munshi and the anticipated support of Baldev Singh, Jagjivan Ram and Sri Prakash, Patel was prepared to confront Nehru's China policy. However, his untimely absence from the meeting may have changed the course of history. Deeply upset by Nehru's approach to China,

Patel was particularly distressed by India's failure to protect the Tibetan people who had placed their trust in India. He accused the Chinese government of deceit and betrayal, exposing their double-dealing and their calculated aggression against Tibet. Patel's prophetic words are a poignant reminder of the costly consequences of underestimating China's intentions.

Patel's foresight was evident when he warned Nehru about China's real intentions, saying that India considered China a friend, but the feeling was not reciprocated. However, Nehru dismissed these concerns and denied any immediate threat from China. He also rejected Patel's proposal to modernise the Indian Army, citing economic constraints and possible adverse effects on India's overall defence position. Cabinet colleague V.N. Gadgil shared Patel's concerns about China's ambitions and warned about the possibility of Chinese aggression in Tibet and India's northeastern regions.

Patel emphasised the weakness of India's northeastern border, particularly through Nepal, Bhutan and Sikkim, which China could exploit to infiltrate and destabilise India. He warned against any indecisiveness or lack of decisiveness in formulating and implementing India's foreign policy, as it could weaken India's position and exacerbate existing threats. Patel also highlighted the potential security implications of China's growing influence, particularly with regard to the Communist Party of India. He warned that the party could now have easier access to Chinese communist networks and overseas communist organisations, posing a threat to India's internal security.

Had Patel been the decision-maker, he would have taken a more cautious and strategic approach to India's foreign policy, prioritising national security interests. In contrast to Nehru's unwavering support for China's entry into the United Nations, Patel expressed his objections, citing China's aggressive behaviour towards Tibet and its involvement in the Korean War. He questioned the wisdom of advocating for a nation that had repeatedly turned down India's overtures.

The Sino-Indian War of 1962 exposed the flaws of Nehru's idealistic approach to China. His belief in developing friendship through appeasement proved ineffective in curbing Chinese aggression. Patel's foresight, including his suggestion to consider Tibet's independence as a strategic countermeasure, could have significantly altered Asia's geopolitical landscape.

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel's Contribution to Nationalism

Patel inherited a strong sense of nationalism from his father, a veteran of the 1857 revolt. As a child he spent countless winter nights in peasant huts, influenced by his father's stories of the uprising. Soon, he

left his rural roots to work in the busy textile mills of Ahmedabad, the place where Gandhiji would later establish his first ashram. Driven by ambition, Patel studied diligently at night and saved every single rupee. At the age of 33, he finally fulfilled his dream of studying law in London. Unlike Nehru, who frequented the city's elite, Patel immersed himself in the libraries of the Inns of Court. To save money, he would walk ten miles daily between the courts and his modest accommodation. The day he was called to the bar was a turning point. Without hesitation, he booked a ticket home and vowed never to leave India again.

Patel and Nehru were both leaders of independent India, but their visions for the nation were fundamentally different. Patel, a pragmatist, was sceptical of Nehru's idealistic dreams of a socialist utopia, dismissing them as mere rhetoric. He believed in the efficacy of capitalism, and advocated adapting it to Indian realities rather than rejecting it outright. Coming from an industrial city, Patel's outlook was influenced by the tangible world of machines, factories and textiles. In contrast, Nehru's upbringing in Kashmir, a land of natural beauty, influenced his romantic and idealistic outlook.

Patel's focus was entirely on domestic affairs. As home minister, he reformed India's civil services, ensuring their loyalty to the nation rather than the British colonial legacy. While Nehru attracted international attention and assumed the role of Gandhi's successor, it was Patel who commanded the real power and loyalty of the people. Yet, history often overlooks Patel's crucial role. As one of his colleagues rightly put it, Patel was "the last Mughal of India," a leader of immense power and influence whose legacy is often suppressed by the more glamorous Nehru-Gandhi dynasty.

Sardar Patel's vision of nationalism was deeply rooted in the principles of unity and integrity. He believed that a strong and united India was essential for the country's progress and stability. Patel's efforts to integrate the princely states were driven by his commitment to building a coherent national identity. He envisioned an India where regional, linguistic, and cultural differences were respected but did not dominate the collective national identity.

Patel's promotion of Hindi as the national language, though controversial, was aimed at developing a common medium of communication that could unite the diverse population. His belief in secularism and his efforts to protect the rights of minorities further underscored his inclusive vision of nationalism.

In addition to his political endeavors, Patel's speeches and writings inspired a sense of pride and patriotism among Indians. He emphasized the importance of self-reliance, hard work, and devotion to the nation, ideals that still resonate among the Indian public today.

Conclusion

Sardar Vallabhbhai Patel, the "Iron Man of India", is etched in the pages of Indian history as a colossal personality. His unwavering commitment to national unity and integrity, coupled with his strategic brilliance and diplomatic acumen, played a key role in shaping the destiny of independent India. One of Patel's most significant contributions was the integration of over 560 princely states into the Indian Union. Through a combination of persuasion, diplomacy and decisive action, he skillfully handled complex political scenarios and created a unified nation. His strong will and determination played a key role in overcoming many challenges, including the integration of Hyderabad, Junagadh and Kashmir. Beyond his political achievements, Patel's legacy extends to the field of national security. He recognised the importance of a strong and efficient administrative system and played a key role in establishing the All India Services. These services have been the backbone of India's civil administration, contributing to its stability and progress. Patel's unwavering patriotism and his vision for a strong and prosperous India will continue to inspire generations. His life and achievements are a testimony to the power of leadership, courage and unwavering dedication to the nation. As we commemorate his legacy, let us take inspiration from his example and strive to build a strong, united and prosperous India.